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Developing Engineering Students' Entrepreneurial Mindset

Case Study: Technical Innovation Project Course

A. Hänninen

Planning Officer

School of Chemical Engineering, Aalto University

Espoo, Finland

E-mail: anja.hanninen@aalto.fi

A. Santasalo-Aarnio

University Teacher

Department of Chemical and Metallurgical Engineering

School of Chemical Engineering, Aalto University

Espoo, Finland

E-mail: annukka.santasalo@aalto.fi

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INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship as a competence is considered today as one of the key skills needed in the knowledge-based society and economy. It applies to all spheres of life, helping people to develop their skills, knowledge and attitudes needed when achieving their goals.[1] It is not important only for the students aiming to start up an own company, but to all the university students who will enter in the demanding working life, and start building up a career, when life-long learning, and team, leadership and innovation skills are vitally needed.

Teaching entrepreneurial skills during the Master's studies enables to raise the students' awareness of the skills needed in the working life in a complex world. It thus helps them to take ownership of their own success when leaving the university and starting to create their career. The skill set cannot be learned in one go, but it takes

continuum to develop oneself from the beginner's to the advanced or expert level. The entrepreneurship skill set is best learned through experience, in an environment that fosters entrepreneurial thinking and activity [2, 3]. Teacher feedback and self-assessment can give additional support in the progress.

European Commission (EC) has promoted entrepreneurship in education since 2012 [4], and the development of the entrepreneurial education has progressively grown on European level. Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp), a tool for improving the entrepreneurial capacity of European citizens and organizations, was developed by the EC. It introduces key components of entrepreneurship as a competence, a shared conceptual model for entrepreneurial learning, and a list of learning outcomes that anyone can refer to when demonstrating a certain level of proficiency in entrepreneurship competence.[5] Funding for educational development projects which focus on increasing the entrepreneurial skills and mindset, is provided e.g. by the European Innovation and Technology Community (EIT).[6]

This is a case study done in Aalto University where the Technical Innovation Project course was revised as part of an EIT funded project. New teaching and assessment methods were needed for assisting the students to develop their entrepreneurial mindset, and understand that this is the competence needed in the future working life. This paper discusses on how the students' entrepreneurial skills developed during the course: Did students learn entrepreneurial thinking and gain a right kind of mindset for recognizing and solving problems, as indicated in the learning outcomes of the Technical innovation project course?

1 TECHNICAL INNOVATION PROJECT (TIP) COURSE

This course was prepared by modifying an existing technical project work course that had been run at Aalto metallurgical master's program for two decades. In the old project course, a traditional approach was taken as the aim was to solve a technical problem, pre-set by the university staff. The students had to try to reach close to the technical level of the staff, without any industry involvement.

Developing a new course became possible in the fall 2016 within another, EIT RawMaterials funded, educational project which included a 'training the trainers' session, and personal mentoring for a course development – explained in detail in our previous work [6]. The entrepreneurial teacher mentoring, provided by the Aalto Ventures Program, offered support for the teachers in implementing entrepreneurial mindset into the technical teaching practice.

The new TIP course was piloted in the fall 2017, and this study has been conducted during the pilot. Students with two different academic backgrounds met on this course: 2nd year master's students from the Sustainable Metals Processing program at the School of Chemical Engineering (SMP; 8 students, where 0 female), and 1st year master's students from the international joint program European Mining Course (EMC; 15 students, 3 female). This led into a group of altogether 23 students, having

knowledge in both mining and metallurgy, which is a possible skills scenario also in the working life teams. The Intended learning outcomes for the new course are:

- The student can share his/her expertise in a multidisciplinary team
- The student can evaluate added value of process, service or product
- The student can present findings in an international seminar
- Creates international network of peers and company representatives

According to the TIP course's learning outcomes, the students learn to use entrepreneurial thinking in problem solving by understanding the customer needs and how their solution can bring added value. In addition, the aim is that the students recognize their own expertise as well as their role and input in the teamwork, by reflecting with their multidisciplinary teammates. One tool in this recognition process is the self-assessment questionnaire where students can follow their learning progress.

The old project work course had two different parts: advanced lectures on the current topics given by professors, and a technical problem-solving project. The students presented their findings in a written report and oral presentation; the tasks were prepared individually. As the students are in the final stage of their studies, the first modification of the new course was to change the lecture part into workshops where students learn working life related skills, entrepreneurial mindset and leadership. The focus was not on providing information but rather on practising these skills through different exercises, partly prepared at home and partly at the workshops. They prepared weekly personal and professional development logs, in order to support their professional growth by reflecting. The aim was to get the students to reflect on the experiences they already had from working on their field (summer jobs), and have a safe environment to try out different methods in the workshops. This reflective work was individual, and along with the points from the workshops provided them 50 % of the course grade.

The other part (and 50 % of the course grade that was common to the project team) was the project work prepared in teams of 3-4 students. The team approach was selected as in the working life many of the projects are executed in multidisciplinary teams, and this far during the master's studies the students had prepared most of their tasks individually. The idea of the project was not a pre-set problem solving, but instead the teams were given a theme: *"Understanding the whole value chain from ore to metallic product"*. As the students came from two different majors, they needed to combine their knowledge in order to obtain high results in the project. After this, the project leaders were selected, and with the industrial representatives nine more detailed focus areas were chosen, such as *"Arsenic in the metallurgy process"*, *"wastewaters"* or *"future of metals"*. As presented in Fig. 1, the idea of the entrepreneurial mindset project is as in any entrepreneurial action: listen to the clients, discover and identify issues and problems that need to be solved. The first interviews with the company were set for the students in order to get them to start the projects

as soon as possible. The teams interviewed the company representatives, and carefully listened to which issues there would need solving. After that, they decided in teams, which were the problems in their area they would start working with.

Fig. 1 Schematic presentation of the entrepreneurial mindset project work flow.

The timeline of the course teamwork is presented in *Table 1* where it can be seen that a lot of time was committed for discovering a proper problem. For most of the students this was a new experience, and they felt a bit uncomfortable, but discovering their own problem got them very motivated working on their tasks. The teams presented these problems as pitch presentations, and got feedback on the relevance of the discovered problems from the university staff. After the feedback, following the iterative loop, most of the groups modified their problem, and conducted more interviews with industrial representatives in order to get a better view on how to focus more in the problem. In the next pitch, also the original company mentors were present for providing their feedback.

Table 1. Timeline of the entrepreneurial mind-set project

Week	Project timeline	Week	Project timeline
37	Team building and preparing the agreement	44	EMC at Excu (interviews), further validation
38	Interviews of client - > identify needs	45	Feedback 3: Validated 3 solutions
39	Feedback 1: Customer needs + agreements	46	Visual Angle
40	Further interviews - wider angle	47	Final Presentations
41	Stakeholder analysis – identifying the players	48	Project reflection
42	Feedback 2: Description of relevant problem	49	Course reflection
43	Brainstorming 100 solutions - Selection of 3 solutions and validation	50	-

After the second pitch session, the teams brainstormed altogether 100 solutions and selected the three most relevant ones to continue with. The idea behind the large number of solutions is that it forces the students to provide other than the most obvious solutions (might first sound ridiculous, but can give other team members ideas for modifying them further). After this, the students validated these three ideas, and pitched them for the staff. The validation could be a technical one, or based on customer interviews or analyses, but furthermore an economical evaluation was needed, too. From the feedback of this pitch, the teams could decide what to present as their final results, and what to focus on in order to have a deeper knowledge of the

idea they would present in a seminar to the university staff, and the company representatives.

As the students are less familiar with working on this kind of projects, the workshops supported their task: e.g. how to have a proper brainstorming session, or provide constructive feedback, about leadership, team forming and reflection by utilizing art. In addition, the students needed a lot of guidance with their work. It turned out that many of the teams would have benefitted from weekly mentoring sessions (that will be implemented in the course next academic year). The feedback from the pitching sessions was extremely valuable, but added to the verbal feedback, the staff wanted the students to know with which grade their project was pre-evaluated. For this purpose, a bonus system was used: for ordinary performance, the team just obtained "ordinary salary" but for the teams that had well understood what was expected and whose project was pre-evaluated with a high grade, an additional cash bonus was given (not real money though). The bonus was announced in front of all the teams, so the teams could benchmark themselves in comparison with others. Some found this a very helpful indication on how their team was performing in this new task.

Four short videos on how the course was conducted, can be found in Youtube:

Part 1: Assignment <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ps-BeyrUHHU>

Part 2: Feedback <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9oCnnDjbEKA>

Part 3: Validation <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IA07ZGZHsp0>

Part 4: Using Art <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xqNeZLnyHpA>

2 THE SELF-ASSESSMENT

In order to address the research question at this course, the students performed self-assessment as part of their personal and professional development log. The students evaluated their own performance on the following questions at the beginning and at the end of the course. The evaluation uses a scale from 1 to 5 where the mentioned competence is (1) not recognizable, (2) insufficient, (3) developing, (4) good, or (5) excellent.

Table 2. The average of the student self-assessment at the beginning and at the end of the course, and the difference between them.

	Question	Beginning	End	Difference
1	I recognize my own professional strengths	3.59	4.31	0.72
2	I am competent in working in teams	3.91	4.24	0.33
3	I recognize the roles I take in different teams	3.36	4.29	0.92
4	I am able to communicate my ideas to others in team	4.00	4.29	0.29
5	Leadership	3.27	3.67	0.39
6	I am able to provide constructive feedback	3.50	4.10	0.60
7	I am able to present my findings for large audience	3.32	4.14	0.82
8	I am able to identify customer needs	3.27	3.71	0.44
9	I am experienced in professional reflection	2.36	3.64	1.28

As the TIP course students are on advanced level, they already possessed to some extent many of these work related skills. Especially, they felt they already had skills in teamwork and in sharing ideas with team-members. Yet, they were not so confident in leadership, identifying customer's needs, recognizing their role in a team or presenting their findings for larger audience, because this has not been in the focus of their previous studies. Most of them had insufficient or no skills in personal reflection before the course. The TIP course purpose was to provide them more of these skills, and help them to recognise their professional growth before they exit the university.

At the end of the course, the students evaluated having good or excellent skills in recognizing their own professional strengths. According to the course teacher, this is a very good result. The TIP course is placed ideally in the master's studies, right before the student needs to find the Master's thesis project. Recognizing one's strengths is an asset for the student, and it helps him/her to find a good thesis project. The students also evaluated having very high skills in working in teams (recognizing their role, sharing their ideas and feeling competent). As well, the presentation skills improved significantly with all the students during the course. However, the leadership skills were not reported to change that much, which according to the teacher, could be related to the fact that only one student in each team had the leadership position. The biggest difference shown was with the professional reflection skills, mainly due to the very low starting level. This is an excellent result as reflection is a very important tool for life-long learning. As the students would benefit on these skills during their entire study time, an introduction to these skills should come already earlier on their study path, says the teacher. On this course, the reflection is based mainly on the students' own working life experiences.

Overall, the students evaluated that almost all of their evaluated skills had improved during the course, and at the end, they reported to have a 'developing or good' entrepreneurial skills level. The aim of the self-assessment was to help the students reflecting their own competence levels, and help themselves to see the development of the desired skills.

3 ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETENCE FRAMEWORK (ENTRECOMP)

EntreComp is a comprehensive, flexible and multipurpose reference framework designed to help you understand what entrepreneurship as a key competence means for lifelong learning. [5]

EnterComp is made up of three competence areas: Ideas & Opportunities, Resources, and Into Action. Each area consists of 5 competences, making altogether 15 competences. Beneath each competence, there are a number of different threads, describing what the particular competence really means in practice. Each thread has associated learning outcomes across 8 progression levels with increasing level of autonomy of the learner and decreasing external support: foundation, intermediate, advanced and expert.

3.1 Comparing the self-assessment results with EntreComp

The self-assessment results compared with the EntreComp progression levels show that our students mainly have competences in the foundation, intermediate and advanced levels, as far as the progression levels are comparable. In the *Table 3*. we can see that all the three competence areas of EntreComp are covered by the TIP self-assessment.[5].

Table 3. Self-assessment compared to respective main competences in EntreComp

Question	Competence area	Competence(s)
1	Ideas & Opportunities, Resources, Into Action	creativity, self-awareness & self-efficacy, motivation & perseverance, learning through experience
2	Into Action	working with others
3	Resources	mobilizing resources
4	Into Action	working with others
5	Into Action	taking initiative, planning & management, working with others, learning through experience
6	Resources	mobilizing resources
7	Resources	mobilizing others
8	Ideas & Opportunities	spotting opportunities, creativity
9	Into Action	learning through experience

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this case study, a traditional technical project work course was transformed into a new project course that supports students' entrepreneurial competence growth. With the students' self-assessment, the success of this change was studied. The new course involves, not only multidisciplinary teamwork where students by interviewing company representatives discovered a relevant problem to focus on, but also workshops that support the development of the students' entrepreneurial personal and team skills.

As the students evaluated their own competences, they could recognize their increased skills and knowledge, and learn to position their competences better on a given scale. This, leading to a greater self-awareness, will improve their ability to promote themselves to potential employers after graduating from university [1].

Part of the new methods used here still need improving, as this is a very different and new approach for the student project works. The students needed a lot of support in identifying relevant real-life problems, and developing a clear picture of them. However, after the course, most of them felt very enthusiastic and connected to their projects as while looking for solutions they felt they could influence on their tasks. It was not possible for any student to prepare this project alone, but teamwork and knowledge from different academic backgrounds was needed.

Students learn entrepreneurial thinking via solving real life problems, and motivated students create something out of their personal interest. Learning should not be strongly directed from outside as motivated learning can turn into a process where new knowledge and innovations are created. [2, 7]

EntreComp seems a useful tool for anyone in helping to understand the entrepreneurship competence as a whole. For assisting students in developing their entrepreneurial skills, supporting materials and tools are welcome. EntreComp is a good material for teachers, and for students. As there is a promise of a self-assessment tool based on the EntreComp framework to be developed [1], we are looking forward to trying it on the next execution of the TIP course. A matching tool would enhance the results' evaluation both for the students themselves, and for the teachers.

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